

EVALUATION OF MODULAR PERFORMANCE-BASED TASK FOR SPECIAL PROGRAM IN SPORTS

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Evaluation of Modular Performance-Based Task for Special Program in Sports

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Abstract

This study evaluates the effectiveness of modular performance-based activities in the Special Program in Sports (SPS) at Escalante National High School, with a particular focus on their potential to enhance the athletic and holistic development of student-athletes. The evaluation of the relevance and impact of these tasks in specialized areas, such as sports education, has become increasingly critical with the transition to modular and remote learning. The study examines the demographic profiles of SPS students, assesses the perceived efficacy of modular tasks, and examines variations in effectiveness with respect to gender and sports discipline. A descriptive correlational design was employed to analyze data from 100 Grade 7–10 SPS pupils, which were collected using a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS. The results showed that modular performance-based tasks were highly effective ($M = 4.029$), with athletics being the most effective, closely followed by volleyball, *Sepak Takraw*, and basketball. The modular approach's adaptability and equity were illustrated by the absence of substantial disparities based on gender or sports discipline. The challenges that have been identified include the necessity of maintaining student motivation and the limited accessibility of resources. The research suggests that modular assignments are effective in evaluating and developing skills, thereby facilitating the acquisition of essential life skills and athletic abilities. Providing educators with professional development, providing ongoing feedback, instituting inclusive practices, and enhancing resource accessibility are among the recommendations. Future research should examine the long-term effects of these tasks on physical health and career preparedness in order to enhance the educational value of SPS programs.

Keywords: Modular Learning, Assessment Effectiveness, Performance-based Tasks, Sports education

INTRODUCTION

Physical activity plays an essential role in the holistic development of young people, enhancing not only their physical health but also their social and emotional well-being. Beyond its physical benefits, sports education offers critical educational and developmental advantages. It fosters an environment where students, particularly athletes, become central to the learning process, with physical activities serving as tools for purposeful education. By integrating physical activity into the curriculum, educators aim to shape students' intrinsic motivation and attitudes toward lifelong health and fitness, encouraging sustained physical activity habits (Moeijes et al., 2019). The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines introduced the Special Program in Sports (SPS) to support students with potential in various sports disciplines, creating a pathway for these students to compete nationally and internationally. The SPS also aims to prepare graduates for careers in sports and related fields, as well as for further academic pursuits. The program's policies, defined in DepEd Order No. 25, s.2015, prioritize enhancing athletic potential, balancing academic and sports commitments, and preparing students for future professional or educational

opportunities. DepEd Order No. 8, s.2015 also established a rigorous assessment system, requiring annual pre- and post-performance profiles for each student-athlete in their chosen discipline. However, recent global disruptions have halted athletic events and training, forcing athletes and schools to adopt alternative strategies for maintaining their routines and skill development (Andreato, Coimbra, & Andrade, 2020).

With the shift to modular learning, many schools have adapted their SPS programs to remote and independent study, a change that has introduced significant challenges in evaluating performance-based tasks. Performance-based assessments, known for their instructional advantages, enable teachers to gauge students' progress toward learning objectives, particularly in active and skill-based areas such as sports. These assessments provide insight into students' competencies by focusing on actual performance rather than theoretical knowledge, making them particularly valuable in physical education (Ozan and Kınca, 2018; Human Kinetics, 2021).

Despite the prevalence of modular learning across the globe, there has been limited research on the

effectiveness of performance-based tasks within this format, especially in specialized fields like sports. This gap highlights the need for studies that examine how modular systems affect skill acquisition and assessment in sports education, which this research aims to address (Arjona, 2022). Additionally, assessment of performance tasks in the SPS faces several unique challenges. Ambiguous instructions can confuse students, resulting in misrepresentation of their skills or knowledge.

Furthermore, limitations in assessment tools may impede the alignment between performance tasks and students' learned content, compromising the accuracy of evaluations (Ozan and Kınca, 2018). The absence of immediate feedback due to the lack of inperson interactions limits students' ability to make real-time adjustments in their skills (Jeffery & Bauer, 2020). Similarly, students may lack access to the necessary resources, such as sports equipment and facilities, which are crucial for demonstrating specific competencies. These disparities can impact both the fairness and effectiveness of assessments (Herman & Cook, 2019). Finally, the modular setup poses challenges in maintaining student motivation and discipline, as the lack of peer presence and direct supervision can diminish students' drive to practice and refine their skills (Meşe & Sevilen, 2021).

This study thus seeks to evaluate the modular performance-based tasks among students in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School, with the aim of informing a redesign of these tasks that aligns more closely with the demands and limitations of the new normal in education.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the Modular Performance-Based tasks among Special Program in Sports students of Escalante National High School as a basis for redesigning the performance task in the new normal.

Specifically, this study will answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents according to:
 - a. Sex
 - a.1 male
 - a.2 female
 - b. Sports Discipline
 - b.1 athletics
 - b.2 basketball
 - b.3 sepak takraw
 - b.4 volleyball

2. What is the level of effectiveness of the modular performance-based task on students among special program in sports?
3. Is there a significant difference on the evaluation of the effectiveness of the modular performance-based task among special program in sports students when grouped according to sex and sports discipline?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a descriptive correlational research design to examine relationships between variables without establishing causation. Descriptive research, as Ebipere (2022) explains, aims to systematically describe a population or phenomenon, focusing on "what" and "how." According to Abdulai and Owusu-Ansah (2014), descriptive research provides a structured account of a scenario, service, or community context, while correlational research identifies relationships between two variables without researcher control (Ebipere, 2022). This design was chosen to assess the effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks in the Special Program in Sports.

Research Environment and Research Participants

This study involved students enrolled in the Special Program in Sports from Grades 7 to 10 during the 2021-2022 academic year. The sample size was determined using Cochran's formula, which calculates an ideal sample size based on the desired level of precision, confidence level, and estimated proportion within the population (Hasan & Kumar, 2024). This formula, widely used for its simplicity, provides an efficient way to ensure reliable results with minimal prior population information.

To enhance representativeness, stratified random sampling was employed. As Hayes (2020) describes, stratified random sampling divides the population into sub-groups or "strata" based on shared characteristics, ensuring each group is proportionately represented. Here, the researcher calculated the sample size from the entire student population within the Special Program in Sports at a secondary school in Negros Occidental, then used stratified random sampling to select participants from each grade level, achieving a well-distributed sample across grades.

Research Instrument

This study employed a researcher-developed questionnaire to collect data, utilizing a Likert Scale with the following interpretations: 5 for "Extremely Effective," 4 for "Very Effective," 3 for "Effective," 2 for "Somewhat Effective," and 1 for "Not Effective." The questionnaire was structured into two main parts. Part 1 gathered demographic information about the respondents, while Part 2 consisted of 20 items evaluating specific aspects of the performance-based tasks. This section included five items focused on the content quality of the tasks and another five items assessing instructional delivery across cognitive, affective, psychomotor, and social dimensions, aimed at measuring the effectiveness of the tasks in meeting performance objectives.

Prior to implementation, the questionnaire was pilot-tested to ensure reliability and validity, refining items as necessary to enhance clarity and accuracy in capturing respondents' assessments.

Data Analysis

A statistician conducted the data analysis using SPSS software. To address problem number 2, which aimed to assess the effectiveness level of modular performance-based tasks for teachers and students in the Special Program in Sports, the mean and standard deviation were calculated. For problem number 3, which investigated significant differences in students' evaluations based on gender, an Independent Samples T-Test was applied. Additionally, to examine significant differences in evaluations across different sports disciplines, ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was used.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first sought permission to conduct the study from the Division of Escalante City, addressing the request to the Division Education Program Supervisor in MAPEH. Upon receiving the necessary authorization, the researcher informed participants about the purpose and objectives of the study. Survey questionnaires were then distributed to the participants, who completed them at their convenience. Once finished, the researcher collected the completed questionnaires to proceed with data analysis.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to strict ethical standards to ensure the rights and well-being of all participants. Participation was entirely voluntary, with no pressure or

misleading information influencing respondents' decision to take part. Throughout all phases—from data collection to publication—the anonymity and confidentiality of participants were meticulously protected. If the researchers intended to disclose any identifying information, explicit permission was obtained from the participants in advance. Identifiable details, such as names and physical locations, were removed before any publication of results.

Data analysis was conducted in a private, distraction-free environment to maintain focus and respect the confidentiality of responses. During data transcription, all identifying information, including names and other personal details, was omitted. In presenting the study's findings, participants were referred to by pseudonyms, ensuring privacy even within verbatim quotes. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any repercussions or persuasion to continue. This commitment to ethical standards reflects the study's respect for participant autonomy and the integrity of the research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussion based on the qualitative data gathered from 100 Grade 7 to 10 students enrolled in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School for the school year 2021-2022. The analysis includes the demographic profile of the respondents, their sports disciplines, and the perceived effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	77	77.0	77.0	77.0
Female	23	23.0	23.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 displays the demographic breakdown of the participants according to sex, showing that 77% of the students in the Special Program in Sports are male, while 23% are female. According to a study by Hopkins et al. (2022), various factors influence girls' participation in sports, including personal, peer, family, socioeconomic, and environmental factors. Among these, personal perceptions of self and desirable outcomes (e.g., enjoyment, health benefits) are often the most influential. This finding indicates that female

participation is significantly impacted by social factors, such as friendships, economic conditions, and environmental support, which play a role in encouraging their engagement in sports activities.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Sports Discipline

Sports Discipline	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Athletics	31	31.0	31.0	31.0
Basketball	48	48.0	48.0	79.0
Sepak Takraw	9	9.0	9.0	88.0
Volleyball	12	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 2 outlines the distribution of respondents by sports discipline. Thirty-one percent (31%) specialized in athletics, 48% in basketball, 9% in Sepak Takraw, and 12% in volleyball. According to Eastwood College (2019), sports provide students with a means of staying fit and offer broader developmental benefits, teaching essential life skills such as teamwork, accountability, self-confidence, responsibility, and self-discipline. DepEd Order No. 25, s.2015, specifies that schools offering the Special Program in Sports should provide a curriculum integrating the K-12 Basic Education Program with specialized sports training, allowing students who meet admission criteria to focus on athletics or team sports like volleyball, Sepak Takraw, and basketball.

Table 3: Mean Scores of Perceived Effectiveness of Modular Performance-Based Tasks by Sports Discipline

Sports Discipline	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Athletics	4.0694	31	0.79222
Basketball	3.9958	48	0.92758
Sepak Takraw	4.0278	9	1.02656
Volleyball	4.0583	12	1.26793
Total	4.0290	100	0.92930

Table 3 shows the mean scores of students' perceptions of the effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks across various sports disciplines. The results indicate that students specializing in athletics perceived a higher effectiveness level ($M = 4.0694$, $SD = 0.79222$) compared to those specializing in volleyball ($M = 4.0583$, $SD = 1.26793$), Sepak Takraw ($M = 4.0278$, $SD = 1.02656$), and basketball ($M = 3.9958$, $SD = 0.92758$). Despite differences, all students reported a high level of perceived effectiveness. Performance tasks are essential

in engaging students through real-world applications of knowledge and providing teachers with a means of assessing complex skills.

The results further show that the modular performance-based tasks were effective overall, with a mean score of 4.029. This modality, favored by the Special Program in Sports, allowed teachers to use performance tasks as a training tool and for assessing students' progress in both practice and competition settings.

Table 4: Comparison of Perceived Effectiveness of Modular Performance-Based Tasks by Sex

Sex	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Male	77	49.25	3792.50
Female	23	54.67	1257.50
Total	100		

The analysis showed no significant difference in the perceived effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks when grouped by sex. Zhan et al. (2015) emphasize that grouping by gender can significantly impact learning attitudes, while Albay and Eisma (2021) suggest using varied strategies in performance-based assessments. Overall, both male and female students found the tasks equally effective, indicating that the modular performance-based approach serves as a fair assessment tool for all students in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School.

Table 5: Comparison of Perceived Effectiveness of Modular Performance-Based Tasks by Sports Discipline

Sex	N	Mean Rank
Athletics	31	48.97
Basketball	48	48.98
Sepak Takraw	9	53.00
Volleyball	12	58.67
Total	100	

The analysis indicated no significant difference in the perceived effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks across different sports disciplines. Zhan et al. (2015) point out that grouping by sport can shape learning attitudes, while Albay and Eisma (2021) advocate for varied strategies in performance-based assessments. Overall, students from various sports disciplines found the tasks similarly effective, suggesting that the modular performance-

based approach is a fair assessment tool for all participants in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School.

Findings

Based on the data collected from 100 Grade 7 to 10 students in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School, the following key findings were observed:

Demographic Profile by Sex

The majority of the respondents in the Special Program in Sports were male (77%), while female students comprised 23% of the population. This distribution aligns with findings by Hopkins et al. (2022), which indicate that girls' participation in sports is often influenced by personal and social factors, such as self-perception, enjoyment, health benefits, and encouragement from family and friends.

Distribution by Sports Discipline

Among the respondents, 48% specialized in basketball, 31% in athletics, 12% in volleyball, and 9% in Sepak Takraw. This reflects the program's structure, in accordance with DepEd Order No. 25, s.2015, which mandates a curriculum that integrates both individual and team sports. The distribution also aligns with findings on the benefits of sports, which promote physical health as well as essential life skills like teamwork, accountability, and self-discipline (Eastwood College, 2019).

Perceived Effectiveness of Modular Performance-Based Tasks by Sports Discipline

Students' perceived effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks varied slightly across sports disciplines, with athletics receiving the highest mean score ($M = 4.0694$), followed by volleyball ($M = 4.0583$), Sepak Takraw ($M = 4.0278$), and basketball ($M = 3.9958$). Despite these minor differences, all groups rated the tasks as highly effective. This suggests that the modular performance-based approach is widely regarded as an engaging and beneficial method for developing sports skills, supporting the notion by McTighe (in press) that performance tasks enhance student motivation by providing real-world learning contexts.

Comparison of Effectiveness by Sex and Sports Discipline

No significant differences were found in the perceived effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks when comparing responses by sex or sports discipline. This finding indicates that the modular approach serves as a fair and effective assessment tool for students across different genders and sports specializations. Zhan et al. (2015) noted that gender grouping can influence learning attitudes, yet the results here imply that performance-based tasks are equally effective for both male and female students. Similarly, Albay and Eisma (2021) recommend using varied strategies in performance assessments to accommodate diverse student needs, supporting the adaptability of the modular approach.

Overall Effectiveness of Modular Performance-Based Tasks

The overall mean score for effectiveness was 4.029, signifying that the students in the Special Program in Sports generally perceive modular performance-based tasks as effective. This approach not only allows teachers to assess students' progress but also serves as a flexible tool that can adapt to the diverse needs of sports training and assessment. The findings suggest that this modality enhances the students' learning experience and skill acquisition, particularly in sports contexts, by providing structured and meaningful performance evaluations.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that modular performance-based tasks are perceived as effective tools for learning and assessment among students in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School. The high ratings across different sports disciplines—athletics, basketball, volleyball, and Sepak Takraw—demonstrate that these tasks effectively engage students and foster skill development within the program's diverse athletic focus. The study further reveals that the effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks is consistent across both male and female students, suggesting that this approach serves as an equitable and adaptable assessment method for a range of sports and gender demographics. This adaptability is supported by the lack of significant differences in perceived effectiveness when students are grouped by sex or sports discipline, emphasizing that the modular approach successfully meets diverse educational needs in a fair manner. Overall, the modular performance-based tasks contribute positively to the holistic development of student-athletes, supporting not only

their physical and technical skills but also essential life skills such as accountability, teamwork, and self-discipline. This study underscores the value of modular performance-based tasks as a flexible and effective modality for sports education, capable of enriching the learning experiences of students across various sports disciplines and fostering sustained engagement in physical activities.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness and implementation of modular performance-based tasks in the Special Program in Sports at Escalante National High School:

1. **Enhanced Support for Female Participation.** Given that social and environmental factors significantly impact female participation in sports, it is recommended that the school introduce initiatives aimed at increasing female engagement. These could include targeted workshops, mentorship programs, and peer encouragement campaigns that address the specific needs and motivations of female students in sports.
2. **Resource Accessibility and Equipment Provision.** To ensure that all students have equal opportunities to perform and complete performance-based tasks, the school should provide additional resources and access to sports equipment where possible. Creating resource-sharing programs or designating practice spaces on school grounds may support students who otherwise lack access to the required facilities and equipment.
3. **Incorporating Diverse and Real-World Performance Tasks.** To further engage students and mirror real-world applications of their skills, it is recommended that the Special Program in Sports incorporate diverse and practical performance tasks. These tasks should span cognitive, physical, and social skills, allowing students to experience authentic challenges and build competencies across multiple areas relevant to their discipline.
4. **Gender-Inclusive Training and Assessment Approaches.** Since the effectiveness of modular tasks was consistent across genders, it is advised to continue developing gender-inclusive teaching methods that address diverse learning preferences and strengths. Adapting instructional and assessment methods to be

inclusive will ensure that both male and female students receive the support they need to excel.

5. **Continuous Monitoring and Feedback.** To maintain the perceived effectiveness of modular performance-based tasks, regular monitoring and feedback systems should be established. Teachers should periodically assess the effectiveness of these tasks, gathering input from students to refine and adjust the activities to better suit evolving educational and training needs.
6. **Professional Development for Educators.** Providing ongoing training for educators in designing and assessing performance-based tasks will ensure consistent, high-quality instruction. Workshops or professional development sessions on best practices in performance-based assessment, especially for sports education, would equip teachers with the skills to enhance student engagement and accurately measure progress.
7. **Future Research on Longitudinal Impact.** Finally, further studies are recommended to explore the long-term effects of modular performance-based tasks on students' athletic development and academic achievement. This research could provide deeper insights into how sustained engagement with these tasks influences career readiness and physical health outcomes beyond the program.

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